

Documentation for the Selective Encoding of Music Documents¹

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Abstract

The purpose of this document is two-fold. First, it is a presentation of a pair of formalized schemes for including information about the completeness of an MEI encoding with respect to the extent of the source data represented by the file. We refer to such an encoding as a "Selective Encoding". Second, it is an account of how project-based considerations can dictate which alternative to choose when multiple options are available.

Any responsible encoding agent may have any number of reasons for encoding only a portion of a source, but most of these decisions will be motivated by time and/or interest. That is, an analyst or a project may only be concerned with certain aspects of a musical score, such as incipits, or a particular instrumental part, or recurrences of a theme or motive. There may also be time and budget constraints that do not allow for the labor required to encode multiple sources from beginning to end. In order to facilitate the reuse of such Selective Encodings for different researchers and different applications, a standard method for recognizing what regions and aspects have and have not been encoded in an MEI document should be in place.

What we present here are two different methods. Our more structured method takes advantage of MEI's capacity to create customized schemas. It features both new and repurposed elements and attributes to model a music encoding as the complete collection of a source's encoded and unencoded sections. Each section is provided a unique ID and a set of parameter values that allow for easy-to-find and easy-to-read metadata regarding the extent of the score's digital representation. Our simpler method works within already existing MEI structures and is essentially a clarification of existing usage, taking advantage of element entailments along with text descriptions to identify and retrieve encoding information from an MEI file. It is thus a matter of documentation, rather than modification or customization of MEI.

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While we had considered various possibilities for developing a metadata structure to handle these cases, and consulted with the wider MEI community for input and feedback, the team responsible for the *Beethoven in the House* project, for reasons described below, ultimately decided on the simpler format, illustrating how there is often no single best solution for any particular encoding need.

Status of This Document

This document is meant to serve as an exploration of an MEI mechanism to handle Selective Encodings: **Option 1** (the "More Complex" Proposal) in this document.

For reasons detailed below, however, we anticipate that the music encoding community will prefer our second option, formalizing the function and use of existing elements and attributes as described in **Option 2** (the Simple Proposal).

- **Option 1** was workshopped with the MEI Metadata Interest Group in March and April of 2022, though not as an official IG project. It was further refined in project discussions through October 2022.
- **Option 2** was derived through internal project discussions in May and June of 2022, weighing project needs and tooling requirements of complementary applications alongside existing standards and practices within the MEI community.

➤ *Feedback and suggestions are welcome:* info@domestic-beethoven.eu.

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Introduction

One of the largest barriers to digital musicology is the time required to create an encoded music file. While tools exist to automate parts of the process, (format converters for music notation software, for example, or OMR methods such as those for parsing measures) most of the symbolic content—pitches and rhythms—need to be entered manually.

We cannot assume that a single scholar, or even a funded research project, can transcribe the complete corpus of music that might be relevant to their investigations – including any

comparison or control groups – prior to research commencing. Even producing a complete digitisation by the end of their investigations may prove impractical. A better approach would accommodate images or partial editions – transcriptions of only a few bars or one instrumental part – created incrementally as the research progresses.

There is currently no structured way to record metadata regarding which specific sections or aspects of a score have been encoded. Although a text description in prose is possible, machine-readable information can only be inferred from the presence or absence of specific elements within the **<body>** of the document.

To facilitate the creation of corpora for digital analysis, we have developed a procedure for encoding only the portions of a score relevant to a particular study or investigation and for keeping track of those excerpts in a structured way to allow for their retrieval and reuse. When used with a compliant application such as the Domestic Beethoven Annotator or MEI Friend, the labor required for data entry is greatly reduced, and the researcher is partially relieved of the burden of learning MEI's strict guidelines for structuring data before embarking on a digital musicology project. Our resulting encodings, moreover, can be extended at a later time, and by any other scholars who have access to them.

An important benefit of this approach is that it facilitates the digital study of new repertoires, including works and composers that may otherwise go unexamined, especially in a digital context, given that many existing encodings are a result of institutional priorities and funding initiatives that focus on large-scale digitization projects of composers already well represented in print editions and secondary literature.²

Of course, there are other reasons related to the source itself that may result in a partially encoded work. Sketches that are themselves incomplete, or library holdings that include a score for a single instrumental part rather than the complete set. Our methods are intended for these cases as well.

What we present here is actually a pair of solutions, developed in the course of musicological research and the development of an online tool to facilitate that work.

Our structured option ([more complex proposal](#)) presents components for a customized schema in MEI to provide more machine-readable detail in the header, treating it as editorial policy comparable with other header metadata. At the same time, it provides more human-readable metadata as well, so that one need not load an MEI file into an application for processing in order to view what portion of the piece is encoded. That information is available in a list-like format near the beginning of the document in the **<meiHead>**. A small set of new

² "Universities often focus their efforts on large-scale digitization of hegemonic texts, such as literary corpora by white European male authors, liturgical manuscripts, or Western early music editions, which again reinforces canonization." A. Kijas, "What does the data tell us? Representation, canon, and music encoding," 2018. Keynote at Music Encoding Conference, Maryland, 24 May 2018.

elements and attributes are required to support this and thus involves changes to the MEI standard.

Our second option ([simple proposal](#)) adds no new elements or attributes and is essentially a clarification of existing usage, taking advantage of element entailments along with prose descriptions of encoding and sampling policy in the MEI header (`<meiHead>`). All other information about selection decisions are attached to the most relevant local elements (in the `<body>` itself).

Aims of the Selective Encoding Model

To ensure interoperability of MEI encodings, especially for editing applications, there needs to be a clear and unambiguous way of identifying what material has been encoded and, often, what has been left unspecified. Researchers do not want to go to the trouble of searching and accessing an encoding of a work only to load it into an MEI compatible app and find that it consists only of a few measures of encoded music. In addition, if a researcher is interested in a work that already has some existing material encoded, they should be able to add the portion of the score they are interested in to the same file, enriching the encoding and thereby making it more valuable to other scholars. This approach not only allows a greater number of musicologists access to new digital tools that may enhance their research, but also encourages the inclusion of a wider variety of musical sources, given that researchers can choose repertoire themselves and not rely on pre-existing repositories of encoded works by canonical composers.

Another reason for proposing a standard procedure for working with partially encoded works is to facilitate interoperability in a workflow that does not simply allow for such encodings, but rather assumes that encoding is always an incremental process, whether by a single encoder or an open community. There is always more information that can be added, whether that is musical data conveyed through notation, analytic information, editorial decisions, or bibliographic and other metadata.

Currently, the MEI element `<mei:samplingDecl>` provides a place for "a prose description of the rationale and methods used in sampling texts in the creation of a corpus or collection." It is not explicitly designed for an encoding of a work that is in some way incomplete, or partially realized (e. g. a sketch), yet it is explicitly not restricted from being used for this purpose. (The element is modeled on the TEI element `<tei:samplingDecl>` and has been adopted unchanged for use in MEI.) The element allows for no more internal structuring than a `<head>` and `<p>` elements. Nor are the elements systematically linked to any music structures in the encoding.

Terminology

A **Selective Encoding** is any MEI document that contains a **<body>** element with musical data, but is not a complete transcription of the source.

- It is important to acknowledge that *every* encoding is in some sense a selective encoding. A digital encoding of a notated source is a transcription, and in any transcription some features are going to be prioritized at the expense of others. Researchers have different needs and different purposes for their encodings. Not every encoder will assign significance to every mark on the page. And some degree of interpretation is necessary when deciphering symbols: editorial decisions are always being made at every level. The choice transcribers have is how explicit to be about what has been encoded.

With this conception of encoding in mind, the **Selective Encoding** is therefore **an encoding that is *explicit* about its selectivity**.

File Naming and Version History

We anticipate an increased availability and use of applications that facilitate the transcription and editing of music sources (for example, the web app [MEI-Friend](#)). By relieving researchers of the burden of learning MEI's strict guidelines for structuring data before embarking on or contributing to a digital musicology project, such applications have the potential to generate a wealth of Selective Encodings for individual projects. Such encodings can be extended by other scholars who have access to them, and may go through several stages as newly transcribed portions are added to the file. To encourage the reuse and enrichment of these encodings, there needs to be a standard way to identify what parts of a score have been encoded in each file. If we presume a workflow where newly transcribed portions of a work are added to an existing MEI file, it makes sense to match the title of the encoding with the title of the source—with no qualifications regarding extent.

Selective Encoding Schemes

Method 1

This proposal modifies the structure of the **<samplingDecl>** element by providing a *comprehensive listing* of encoded and unencoded sections of the source work in the header,

similar to the use of **<notesStmt>** as a parent element to gather together individual **<annot>** elements.

Model

New or repurposed elements and attributes

- **<section>**
 - Delineates a part of the music we are encoding and gives it an **@xml:id**; distinguishes arbitrary segments of music.
 - Standoff markup is used for information about the extent, sampling method, rationale for inclusion, etc. Uses a **@decls** attribute to reference a **<sample>** in header.
 - All content within a Selective Encoding (including omissions) SHOULD be contained in at least one **<section>**. This allows description of Selective Encoding practice elsewhere in the document.

- **<samplingDecl>**
 - Contains a collection of **<sample>** and **<gap>** elements that should account for all parts of a source, along with optional summary statement in **<p>** element.

- **<range>**
 - Contains inclusive measure numbers of sample (where applicable)
 - Recommend use with **@unit**.
 - Indicate range as element content
 - e.g., `<range unit="measure">1-8</range>` or use with:
 - **@min, @max**

- **<gap>**
 - **<gap>** in the **<body>** indicates that some content in the source has not been realised in the encoding.
 - **<gap>** can be qualified with **@extent** for cases where we want to be explicit about how much is omitted (but this may be confusing in long gaps covering repeats, etc.).
 - **<gap>** in **<sampleList>** contains **@corresp** with the **@xml:id** of the relevant **<section>**.

- **<sample>**
 - A single **<section>** chosen for encoding.
 - MUST be numbered with **@n**, preferably consecutive from "1".
 - MUST have **@corresp** with one or more **@xml:ids**, which SHOULD be **<section>** elements where possible.
 - Optional (encouraged) **@reason** for selection
 - Optional (encouraged) **@aspect** of encoding
 - e.g., full, part/staff, pitch only, harmony
 - Optional (encouraged, if applicable) **@startid**, **@endid** to indicate range of encoded sample.³ (If sample discontinuous, then N/A.)
 - Optional (encouraged, if applicable) measure **<range>** of **<sample>** as child element
 - recommend use of **@unit** for **<range>**
 - Indicate range as element content (e.g., "1-8") or use with
 - **@min**, **@max**

- **@reason**
 - An attribute in **<sample>** that records the reason the selection was chosen for encoding.

- **@aspect**
 - An attribute in **<sample>** that records the fullness of the encoding or the specific parameters chosen for encoding.
 - e.g., "full [encoding]", "melody only", "just pitch and durations", "measures", "dynamic markings".

- **@unit**
 - Defined values extended to include:
 - "measure"
 - "movement"
 - "strain"
 - *etc.*

³ "In general, it is easier for software to process **@startid** and **@endid** [vs **@tstamp**, **@tstamp2**]. When no other arguments apply, using **@xml:id**-based pointers is therefore the most common way to connect ControlEvents with Events." <https://music-encoding.org/guidelines/dev/content/introduction.html#eventsControlevents>

Example

(Also illustrates alternate ways of handling measure ranges.)

```

<meiHead>
  <encodingDesc>
    <samplingDecl>
      <p>Only measures for comparison with arrangements are encoded</p>
      <sample n="1" xml:id="sample-84901" corresp="section-89953"
        aspect="Fully encoded"
        reason="comparing instrumentation at beginning"
        unit="measure" @min="1" @max="36"/>
      <sample n="2" xml:id="sample-84902" corresp="#section-09372"
        reason="comparing articulation of 2nd theme accompaniment"
        extent="oboe part"
        unit="measure" @min="37" @max="42"/>
      <sample n="3" xml:id=" sample-84903" corresp="#section-37013"
        aspect="measure positions, but no notes"
        resp="#cartographerApp"
        unit="measure">43-360</sample>
      <sample n="1" xml:id=" sample-84904" corresp="#section-71722"
        reason="crescendo to rare fff at bar 190."
        aspect="Fully encoded"
        resp="#bithTeam_lr" isodate="2022-04-26">
        <range unit="measure" min="188" max="192">188-192</range>
      </sample>
      <gap xml:id="s84904" corresp="#section-02655"
        unit="measure" extent="364-420"/>
    </samplingDecl>
  <encodingDesc>
</meiHead>

<body>
...
  <section xml:id="section-89953">
    <measure>...</measure>
    <measure>...</measure> ...
  </section>

```

```

<section xml:id="section-37013">
  <measure/>
  <measure/>
</section>
<section xml:id="section-09372">
  <measure>...</measure>
  <measure>...</measure>
  <measure>...</measure> ...
</section>
<section xml:id="section-71722">
  <measure>...</measure>
  <measure>...</measure>
  <measure>...</measure>
  <measure>...</measure>
  <measure>...</measure>
</section>
<section xml:id="section-02655">
  <gap/>
</section>
...
</body>

```

Method 2

Model

Clarify and refine existing documentation

- If a measure is empty or contains only an empty layer, then it **MUST** be a selective transcription that is omitting content in the measure – by contrast, a measure that is empty in the source **MUST** be encoded using **<mSpace>**.
- The semantic function of the **<gap>** proposed above would be fulfilled by an empty **<layer>** element.
- **<samplingDecl>** CAN be used to explain the selection and editorial. A prose description in a **<p>** element can be supplemented with reference to elements in the musical body by **@xml:id** (for example, by pointing to an encoded **<section>**). Multiple **<samplingDecl>** elements can be used for this purpose (rather than introducing a new **<sample>** element, as proposed above in Method 1).

- Areas where the **@aspect** of Selective Encoding changes (different parts, different parameters, different degrees of specificity, or coded vs uncoded) CAN be delimited using **<section>** elements. In this case, **@resp**, and **@class** can be used to add more information.

This usage maintains idiomatic practice in MEI of elements in the **<body>** pointing back up to the **<meiHead>** for supplementary information/standoff markup.

Example

```
<meiHead>
  <encodingDesc>
    <samplingDecl xml:id="section-84901" type="full">
      <p>Measures for comparison between arrangements are
        encoded</p>
    </samplingDecl>
    <samplingDecl xml:id="sample-84902" resp="#cartographerApp"
      type="measures">
      <p>Measure positions only</p>
    </samplingDecl>
    <samplingDecl xml:id="sample-84903" type="nothing">
      <p>No content transcribed</p>
    </samplingDecl>
  </encodingDesc>
</meiHead>

<body>
...
<section xml:id="measure-89953" decls="#sample-84901">
  <measure>...</measure>
  <measure>...</measure>...
</section>
<section xml:id="measure-37013" decls="#sample-84902">
  <measure/>
  <measure/>...
</section>
<section xml:id="measure-09372" decls="#sample-84903">
  <measure>...</measure>
  <measure>...</measure>
  <measure>...</measure>
</section>
```

```

<section xml:id="measure-02655" decls="#sample-84904">
  <gap/>
</section>
...
</body>

```

Considerations - Pros and Cons

Method 1: A New Model

To facilitate reuse of materials, clear details regarding what portions of the work referenced by the encoding's title statement should be presented in an easily findable and easily readable location in the document. The series of **<sample>** elements in the header give a potential file user an overview of the state the encoding is in. This is preferable to going through the **<body>**, noting sections with **@decl**, and then scrolling through the file to uncover the extent of its encoding. Even when intended for use in an editing application, it would be helpful to be able to determine the contents of a file without loading and processing it first. This additional structure also makes it easier to devise machine processing methods (e.g., XSLT, XQUERY) for retrieving the sampling information.

Method 2: Additional Documentation

A drawback of implementing Method 1 is the need for the MEI community and its technical team to embark on a process of review and approval for the new elements. The process is lengthy and ultimate approval is not guaranteed. In addition, MEI tends to be conservative with respect to changes in the standard. An early adopter of the format was the digital editions community, and much of its development has proceeded with this use in mind. Stability and consistency fosters continued use of the standard and helps ensure maximal reusability of encodings.

MEI is also designed to be customizable. This obviates the need for changes in the standard, but remains a project-level solution. However, if the procedure for indicating the degree and extent of encoding contained in an MEI document is not standardized, it can hinder reuse of a project's data by other researchers.

In addition, in cases where music is encoded for the purpose of annotation, editing applications will, with each annotation, be recording the extent of the encoding. It is likely that information will be duplicated if it is recorded by a user in a **<samplingDecl>** in the header as well – inviting errors and inconsistency in the data. It might be possible to create an XSLT to automatically

calculate the extent of the encoding and insert that information in the header, but that would present a highly complex, labor-intensive programming task (although not an impossible one, to be accomplished at a future date or for another project). This is a strong argument for including a **<samplingDecl>** that is limited to a generic statement about why it consists of empty **<layers>**.